

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING

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Annotation. One of the trickiest aspects of interpreting is simultaneous interpretation, which is the topic of this article. The writers of this article describe the unique features of simultaneous interpreting, including how speech compression and prediction concepts are used in simultaneous translation, and they analyze the advantages and disadvantages of this type of interpreting activity.

Keywords: simultaneous interpreting, word-for-word interpreting, consecutive interpreting, advantages, and disadvantages of simultaneous interpreting.

Introduction. Simultaneous interpreting done by ear while the speaker is still speaking in the original language is known as simultaneous translation. Following the Nuremberg trials (1945–1946), which are remembered as the trial of the former Nazi Germany leaders, this style of translation gained widespread recognition. The consecutive translation had previously been employed in conferences and international meetings.^[1]

The working languages of such events were typically English and French,

¹ Chernov G.V. Theory and practice of simultaneous translation. Moscow: Lenand Publishing House, 2016. 208 p.

but because this trial involved five nations (the USSR, Germany, France, the USA, and Great Britain), it was decided to have court proceedings in four different languages: English, French, Russian, and German. The consecutive translation was not allowed because it would have caused the Nuremberg trial to go on interminably. The decision was taken in favor of simultaneous interpretation, and it was at Nuremberg in 1945 that the first simultaneous interpreter teams one Soviet and one American were introduced. Both teams performed their duties honorably. When working with a multinational audience, simultaneous translation has an edge over consecutive translation, as the Nuremberg Trials demonstrated. Years later, South America and China joined the world community's active activities, which drew experts in the Chinese and Spanish languages. Simultaneous interpretation was challenged by interpreters at the UN, but since 1951, it has been a standard practice not only at the UN but also in other international organizations. The only method to guarantee the structure of an international meeting with a significant number of participants speaking different languages is through simultaneous interpretation. Unlike consecutive interpretation, simultaneous interpretation calls for specialized technical tools as well as the participation of three to four simultaneous interpreters who are well-versed in the event's subject matter. The simultaneous translation process has the following characteristics:

- 1) The speaker's speech and the translation must be parallel. The parallelism of the speaker's speech translation is noted by Chernov V.G. and Komissarov V.N. as the primary characteristic of simultaneous translation, on which the method of teaching simultaneous translation depends, as well as the use of specific translation transformations in this type of translation.
- 2) Tight reliance on the speaker's speech's timing and cadence.

- 3) Translation of segments. In contrast to a consecutive interpreter who translates a paragraph at a time, a simultaneous interpreter translates information as it is received.

It is feasible to highlight both the benefits and drawbacks of this kind of translation based on the aforementioned characteristics. Simultaneous translation advantages:

- a) The language barrier between the speaker and the listeners diminishes when simultaneous interpretation is used to give an uninterrupted perception of the speaker's discourse;
- b) The time of the event is cut in half compared to consecutive translation; This enables the speaker, speaking in a foreign language, to maintain the audience's attention and experience the mood and its reaction;
- c) Several languages can be translated simultaneously for a sizable group of listeners.

Simultaneous translation's drawbacks:

- a) A simultaneous translator needs specialized language and psychological training;
- b) The translator's general mental and physical health is badly impacted by extreme mental stress and constant focus on attention. Since a normal individual cannot listen and talk at the same time, simultaneous interpretation is thought to be a psychophysiological aberration;
- c) The requirement is to hire at least three to four simultaneous interpreters who are equally knowledgeable about the event's subject. This is because simultaneous interpreters work in shifts; an interpreter should only work continuously for a total of 30 minutes;
- d) Simultaneous translation is characterized by a noticeably higher degree of information loss and a much lower level of its absorption. The application of speech prediction and speech compression techniques is related to this

situation. Speech compression can lower the text's syllable count without significantly impairing the speaker's ability to accomplish their communication goal. Only if the simultaneous interpreter is well knowledgeable about the speaker's subject is speech prediction possible. Due to the severely constrained time available for translation, the adoption of these approaches is a requirement.^[2]

Simultaneous translation, however, has more beneficial traits than negative ones when we consider that a certain percentage of words in modern languages do not convey any new information and some of the information is not always received by listeners.

Conclusion. Simultaneous interpretation is now a crucial instrument for world events in today's climate of political unrest. It enables people from many nations to communicate in "the same language," swiftly resolve a variety of issues, and simply aids in mutual understanding. Due to the use of specialized tools and the ability to provide simultaneous translation into multiple languages at once, simultaneous interpretation allows a broad audience of listeners to participate in an event while cutting the time of the event in half compared to consecutive interpretation. Simultaneous translation is being used in fields such as commerce, education, and culture, transcending national and linguistic boundaries. When training simultaneous interpreters, it is crucial to pay close attention to this sort of translation, develop it, and enhance it both methodically and theoretically so that in the future, it will be possible to get excellent results in practice.

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